

CREATING AND IMPLEMENTING AN E-SCHOOL RECORDS MANAGEMENT
SYSTEM:
A CASE STUDY OF MUSHONA PRIMARY SCHOOL IN ZAMBEZI DISTRICT

BY

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ABSTRACT

In the bygone era, prior to the rise of cutting-edge technology, organizations, schools included, heavily depended on manual, paper-based systems to oversee their record-keeping processes. However, the relentless evolution of technology has ushered in an opportune moment to address this long-standing challenge. Our project is a dedicated endeavor aimed at surmounting the hurdles intertwined with archaic paper-based record management systems.

Our undertaking encompasses the development of a robust online school management system, adept at housing a wealth of information concerning schools, educators, and students securely within a digital repository. The design and development phases of the project are underpinned by the substantial use of sophisticated computer software and automated tools, ensuring seamless data storage for future reference.

Our paramount consideration during system design is user-friendliness, as we endeavor to make the system easily navigable, sparing users from redundant data entry tasks. Once the foundational modules are established, an extensive testing regimen is executed to warrant the seamless and effective functionality of the project.

Our project entails the development of an online school management system, equipped with the ability to store comprehensive information about schools, teachers, and students within a secure online database. The project's design and development phases heavily leverage sophisticated computer software and automated tools to ensure data storage for future reference.

We have designed the system with user-friendliness in mind, making it straightforward to use without any redundant data entry. Following the creation of the essential modules, a rigorous testing process was conducted to guarantee the successful functionality of the project

List of Abbreviations

ICT - Information Communication Technology
GRMS - Good Record Management System
RMS - Record Management System
ORMS - Online Record Management System
PMEC - Payroll Management and Establishment Control
SRMS - School Record Management System
ERKS - Electronic Record Keeping System
ERM - Electronic Record Management
ID - Identity
CD-ROM - Compact Disc Read Only Memory
OPAC - Online Public Access Catalogue
UML - Unified Modeling Language
PHP - Hypertext Preprocessor
CSS - Cascading Style Sheets
HTML - Hyper Text Markup Language
AJAX - Asynchronous JavaScript And XML
XML - Extensible Markup Language
DFD - Data Flow Diagram

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Every educational institution must establish an efficient and systematic approach to creating, receiving, maintaining, using, and archiving records. This is vital for effective operations and the accumulation of knowledge, ultimately contributing to the attainment of comprehensive, high-quality education. School administrators require a robust Good Record Management System (GRMS) to effectively manage administrative tasks and support all aspects of teaching and learning within schools.

Educational institutions must establish a systematic and efficient approach to manage their records. This is crucial for the smooth operation and knowledge accumulation that contributes to a high-quality education. School administrators need a robust Good Record Management System (GRMS) to handle administrative tasks and support teaching and learning effectively.

In our modern era, technology continually evolves and reshapes our lives, allowing global connections without relying on traditional paper-based methods. In Zambia, many educational institutions, from schools to universities, have adopted computer systems to replace outdated record-keeping practices. This transition enhances the quality and fairness of education.

However, a significant number of Zambian schools still rely on traditional manual methods to record data about teachers and students. This manual approach is inefficient, time-consuming, and costly, with expenses for paper, printers, and ink adding up. The challenge becomes even more pressing with the increase in student enrollment due to the Zambian government's introduction of free education policies, motivating individuals to return to school.

To address these challenges and align with Zambia's goal of achieving a paperless environment by 2030, we have developed an Online Record Management System (ORMS). This web-based system securely stores school information, teacher records, and student records efficiently, simplifying record management, with a specific focus on Mushona Primary School.

1.1 Background of the Study

Mushona Primary School is situated on the east bank of the Zambezi River within the Zambezi District of North Western Province. It's approximately 7 kilometers from the Zambezi town center and was upgraded to a secondary school in 2016. Although Mushona Primary School began its full operation in 2009, it has not yet been officially established by the Permanent Secretary of the Ministry of General Education.

At Mushona Primary School, the management of teacher and student records is currently a manual process. Individual records are recorded by the teachers and the Deputy Head Teacher. This conventional method of record-keeping is paper-based and involves significant time and effort. Teachers, who are already occupied with daily tasks, are burdened by the time-consuming process of transferring information from paper to digital systems. Moreover, student counts are sometimes based on observations, leading to an increased likelihood of errors. Paper-based systems have the advantage of being easily human-readable and securely storable, impervious to viruses (as per Henry, 1988). However, these benefits are outweighed by the disadvantages, such as the need to print records from a paper-based system, which can slow down operations and lack flexibility.

As a result, there has been a growing interest in introducing electronic record management systems to streamline data capture and long-term storage.

Scope of the Study:

The proposed system is designed to manage specific information pertaining to Mushona Primary School. This includes data on departments, classes, teachers, and students ranging from grades 8 to 12. It is important to note that this system is not a comprehensive School Information Management System; instead, it focuses on School Record Management. The system's capabilities encompass data capture, validation, sorting, classification, calculation, summarization, storage, retrieval, reproduction, and communication of operational data. It will store details related to courses, departments, classes, and comprehensive information about students and teachers, including background information, educational qualifications, and personal details.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The School Record Management System (SRMS) involves the collection, processing, and storage of pertinent information, which is crucial for supporting an organization's management operations. It plays a significant role in providing accurate and timely information necessary for informed decision-making and effective execution of an organization's planning, control, and operational functions. Currently, Mushona Primary School relies on a traditional, manual method for entering and storing student records, which involves the laborious process of handwritten entries on paper records, followed by storage. This approach is not only time-consuming but also entails the need for substantial storage space to accommodate the voluminous paper records.

Retrieving records in this paper-based system is a cumbersome task, requiring administrators to sift through stacks of records to locate the specific record they need. A survey conducted by Mr. Kazanga Victor at Mushona Primary School, with a pupil population of 941, revealed that it takes approximately 15 minutes to retrieve a single required record. This time investment is exacerbated when searching for a larger number of records, such as 500 or 1550 pupils, making the paper-based system highly time-consuming. Additional issues associated with the current system include financial costs, as it is expensive in terms of paper and storage cabinets. For instance, at Mushona Primary School, record-keeping cost the school about K75000 in one term, with approximately K9000 allocated to record management. Moreover, the current system is susceptible to errors, loss of student records, and duplication of information.

Significance of the Study: The significance of this study lies in assessing the impact of the Records Management System on the maintenance of teacher and student records at Mushona Primary School within Zambezi District. The development of this online school records management system introduces features such as record accessibility and report generation, simplifying the institution's operations. This proposed automated system aims to enhance the existing system by eliminating the manual processes. Without the system, administrators would face a laborious task in keeping track of each student's record as they have done in the past. The system was designed to provide easy access to and retrieval of student and teacher information with just a click of a button.

Research Objectives: The research aimed to achieve the following objectives:

1. Develop an online School Records Management System to address the issues associated with paperwork in the school.
2. Design and develop a system that is user-friendly for administrators, teachers, and students to manage records.
3. Create an online school records management system for teachers and students.

Research Questions: The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. Why is there a need for an online school record management system in the school?
2. Who will be the primary users of the developed system?
3. What system design models are necessary to create a fully functional system?
4. How will the system be designed and developed?

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

In this chapter, we provide a concise overview of the literature relevant to Record Management Systems and information management. It furnishes a foundational understanding based on pertinent literature reviews of related works. The chapter encompasses an examination of literature directly pertinent to the project and identifies the gaps within existing systems, which the proposed system seeks to address.

2.1 Definition

Cunningham (2006) has defined records management as the management of any information captured in a reproducible form necessary for conducting business. Salaam (2000) emphasizes the significance of records in modern business, while Arora (2001) asserts that contemporary communities heavily rely on records.

Kevin Smith (2012) characterizes records management as a comprehensive management control of records. According to Kevin Smith and other experts, records management, broadly defined, encompasses forms, reports, the reproduction of written materials, filing retention, microfilming, and related concerns. In its broadest sense, records management encompasses the creation, distribution, maintenance, retention, presentation, retrieval, and disposal of records.

Ginn (2011) defines records management system as the planning, control, direction, organization, training, promotion, and managerial activities associated with records' creation, reading, maintenance, use, and eventual disposition.

According to Alison (2009), records management is the process of organizing, storing, and retrieving data from a specific location.

In essence, a Records Management System (RMS) involves the management of records across an organization throughout their life cycle. This management includes the systematic and efficient control of record creation, maintenance, and disposal, along with the associated business transactions. Records management is integral to operational efficiency and significantly enhances the value of an organization's information assets.

When records exist in paper form, it becomes arduous for users to access the information they need from a sea of physical documents. This challenge can be alleviated by implementing an Electronic Record Keeping System (ERKS), enabling users to conveniently access a wealth of information from a single

digital platform.

Therefore, an Electronic Record Keeping System (ERKS), also known as an Electronic Records Management System in some regions, is an information and computer system equipped with the necessary records management capabilities. Its purpose is to electronically collect, organize, classify, and control the creation, storage, retrieval, distribution, maintenance, use, disposal, and preservation of records throughout their life cycle. ERKS aims to manage records with the desired levels of confidence and integrity by combining the advantages of electronic workflows with established records management principles. Electronic Records Management (ERM) refers to applying records management principles within electronic systems, particularly ERKS, and has gained widespread adoption in public sectors, particularly in developed countries.

2.2 Qualities of a Good Information System

As per Comptroller (1995), a robust information system should exhibit the following qualities:

1. **Efficiency:** The system should allow for seamless input and output by providing a framework for recording and aggregating information. It should quickly collect, edit data, summarize results, and facilitate prompt error correction.
2. **Effectiveness:** A quality information system should be capable of achieving its objectives or those of the organization. It should facilitate timely decision-making by providing up-to-date information to the relevant users.
3. **Performance:** An effective information system should enhance communication among employees and support the efficient dissemination of complex materials throughout the organization.
4. **Timeliness:** The information system should be designed to expedite the capture, storage, and reporting of information in real-time as needed.

2.0 Computerized Information Protection on Student Record.

According to Kyobe (2009), South African universities have highlighted that computerized information security concerns, such as access to information, cyber-crime, privacy, virus attacks, and commercial data mining, have become significant issues in academia today (Myler and Broadbent, 2006). Wamukoya and Mutual (2005) have noted that inadequate security and confidentiality controls are major contributors to the failure in capturing and preserving electronic records within educational institutions in Eastern and Southern Africa. Chinyemba and Ngulube (2005) found that 89% of academics surveyed at the University

of KwaZulu-Natal did not sufficiently protect and secure their electronic records. Jones and Soltren (2005) discovered that 58% of students surveyed had no concerns about privacy risks on social network systems. However, inadequate protection of student information is a serious issue because students may access their peers' information without permission, underlining the need for robust protection of student records.

2.1 Computerized Record/Data Management for Student Records

According to the student records manual prepared by the University of South Florida (Office of the Registrar), the creation and maintenance of student records are fundamental for various purposes:

- Managing the relationship between the institution and the student.
- Providing support, services, and facilities to the student.
- Monitoring the student's academic progress and assessing their achievements both during their time at the institution and afterward.
- Offering post-institutional support to the student.
- Aggregating and analyzing data within student records to inform future strategies, planning, and service provisions.

A student record or data comprises personally identifiable information directly related to the student, including the student's name, student ID, address, parent/family member names, and personal characteristics. Student records may be maintained in various formats, including handwriting, print, microfilm/fiche, computer memory, magnetic tape, cassettes, disks, or diskettes. These records serve to assist offices in achieving institutional goals and documenting student progress and accomplishments in the educational process.

Educational institutions and agencies are obligated to adhere to fair information practices. This entails:

- Informing individuals (e.g., students) about the existence of data systems.
- Identifying the data held about them.
- Providing assurances that the data is used only for intended purposes.
- Granting individuals the opportunity to request amendments or corrections to their records.
- Ensuring responsible data system management to prevent misuse of data.

Allen (1989) analyzed studies on patrons' response to bibliographic databases on CD-ROMs in academic libraries and found that patrons preferred CD-ROMs over comparable printed reference tools. Lombardo and Condic (2000) examined user acceptance of Online Public Access Catalogs (OPACs) and discovered

that users overwhelmingly preferred OPACs, finding them easy to use. Similarly, Isman (2004) found that students at Eastern Mediterranean University had a very positive attitude towards Internet use, and Allen (1997) noted that students surveyed were receptive to electronic information resources, with the internet being their most frequently used resource. Idowu (1997) observed that Nigerian university librarians had a positive disposition towards computerized systems.

Computerized records management refers to the management of records in electronic form, as defined by Johnston and Bowen (2005). This includes the creation, usage, maintenance, and disposal of electronically generated records for the purpose of providing evidence of business activities. Archivists emphasize that a 'record' doesn't just represent a collection of data but rather a product or event that reflects and provides evidence of business processes or individual activities (Bantin, 2001).

According to the Scottish Government of Scotland (2008), computerized records management encompasses managing records throughout their life cycle, from creation and usage to maintenance, storage, and eventual destruction or permanent preservation. Muhenda (2000) highlights that proper records management is essential for policy formulation, decision-making, protecting the interests of organizations, safeguarding the rights of employers and students, and facilitating consistent and equitable business operations and service delivery. However, there is limited understanding of computerized records management and compliance with electronic communication regulations among academics and students at Livingstone International University.

2.7 Conclusion

The developed School Record Management System (SRMS) is designed to ensure its longevity by retaining teacher and student records for as long as necessary. This includes fulfilling and discharging the contractual obligations established between the institution, teachers, and students, encompassing academic and non-academic disciplinary actions.

The literature review on the teacher and student information management system has been invaluable in shaping the development of this system. SRMS provides a more efficient means of storing and organizing data compared to traditional spreadsheets. It serves as a centralized platform that is easily modifiable and readily accessible to multiple users. The system features a well-designed user interface that enhances user interaction.

Research from various countries and regions has elucidated the importance of management information

systems in maintaining student records efficiently and providing timely information to students, teachers, and administrators. At Mushona Primary School, issues such as lost marks, incorrect grades, and delays in issuing academic results have posed challenges. However, these issues will be effectively addressed through the utilization of the Online School Record Management System that I have developed.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the research methodology adopted in this study, encompassing research design, population, sample size, sampling methods, data collection methods, the study's procedure, data analysis, study limitations, ethical considerations, and the development tools employed.

3.1 Research Design

The study employed a case study design, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The descriptive design, within this case study, was utilized to describe the phenomenon. Given that this study aims to depict the impact of school records management systems on the maintenance of student and teacher records, the descriptive design was deemed suitable. This approach involved the examination of available documents, interviews, observation of the current system, and the administration of questionnaires to various stakeholders as outlined in the sample size. Examination of documents and research was conducted to ensure clarity and fact verification, utilizing resources like reference books, journals, and the internet. The design phase followed an incremental life cycle model, with the system being divided into components that were designed and built separately in iterations.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population under study consisted of a total of forty (40) individuals, distributed as follows:

Administrators = 6 individuals

Teachers = 12 individuals

Students = 18 individuals

Parents = 5 individuals

3.3 Sample Size

To determine the sample size, the study employed the Slovene formula method. This formula, denoted as $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$, takes into account the population (N) and the sampling error constant ($e = 0.05$). By applying the population of the study to the Slovene formula, the sample size was calculated as follows:

$$N = 40$$

$$e = 0.05$$

Substituting these values into the formula:

$$n = 40 / (1 + 40 * (0.05 * 0.05))$$

$$n = 40 / (1 + 40 * 0.0025)$$

$$n = 40 / (1 + 0.1)$$

$$n = 40 / 1.1$$

$$n \approx 36$$

Therefore, the sample size was determined to be 36.

Table 2: .3.0: population Sample

Category	Population	Sample size
Administrators	6	5
Teachers	10	9
Students	14	13
Parents	5	

Non-students	5	3
Total	40	33

3.4 Sampling Techniques

The study employed a variety of sampling techniques to gather information from different groups of respondents:

Cluster Sampling: This technique was used to collect information from teachers and students.

Systematic Probabilistic Method: This method involved selecting respondents like parents and non-students from a pre-determined list.

Purposive Non-Probabilistic Method: This approach was applied in the collection of information from selected individuals, particularly administrators. Administrators were chosen as they are responsible for managing and controlling the relevant information.

3.5 Data Collection

Data collection involved preliminary investigations to obtain required information, including details about teachers and pupils, personal information, class details, and exam details. These data were essential for identifying the attributes, relationships, classes, and entities that describe and interact with the system. Various data collection tools and techniques were utilized:

Observation: Visiting secondary schools in Zambezi district to observe daily operations and how administrators and teachers recorded data within the paper-based system.

Interviews: Conducting face-to-face interviews to interact with school administration, teachers, and students to obtain the necessary data for the system.

Questionnaires: Distributing prepared questionnaires to school administration, teachers, and students to gather information required for the research.

Data Analysis

The study employed both quantitative and qualitative techniques for data analysis. Qualitative analysis was conducted through thematic coding of the interview data, while the quantitative approach used descriptive statistics such as mean, mode, median, variance, and standard deviation to derive insights from the collected information.

Ethical Considerations

The study prioritized the ethical treatment of respondents. Consent was respected, and respondents were free to leave for exercise without any hindrance. Identity information was kept confidential, and personal opinions were not sought. The study did not harm respondents, and it was strictly conducted for academic purposes.

3.6 Development Tools

The system was designed and developed using both backend and frontend web technologies. The Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP) was used for the system's logical operations, and XAMPP was utilized as the database. The system design employed CSS and HTML with AJAX and JavaScript for scripting purposes.

3.7 System Design

To facilitate the capture, storage, and retrieval of student and teacher records, the data collected was analyzed. The design phase utilized UML Diagrams and DFD (Data Flow Diagrams). The fundamental requirements for designing the school records management system included:

Individual user identity.

Login facility.

User ability to update personal information and view details.

Administrator's full control over the system.

3.7.0 System Requirements

The system's successful operation depended on specific hardware and software requirements, as well as security and operational considerations. A summary of these system requirements

is presented in the table below.

Table 3: 3.7.1 System Requirements

Hardware	Requirement	Software	Requirement
Processor	At least Pentium	Operating system	Windows 7. 8. 10 and 11
Memory	A least 4GB RAM	Application Environment	Visual basic

The design of the system was accomplished by the use of the following techniques; UML diagrams. DFD and physical database design of the school record management system.

3.7.2 Data Flow Diagram

A data-flow diagram is a way of representing a flow of data through a process or a system. The DFD also provides information about the outputs and inputs of each entity and the process itself. A data-flow diagram has no control flow — there are no decision rules and no loops.

Figure 3: Data Flow Diagram

3.7.3 UML Diagrams

UML stands for Unified Modeling Language. It's a rich language to model software solutions, application structures, system behavior and business processes. ULM is in two category types: structure diagrams and behavioral diagrams. The UML used in this study include Use Case Diagram and Class Diagram.

3.7.3.0 Use Case Diagram

As the most known diagram type of the behavioral UML types, Use case diagrams give a graphic overview of the actors involved in a system, different functions needed by those actors and how these different functions interact. It's a great starting point for any project discussion because you can easily identify the main actors involved and the main processes of the system. Therefore the school record management system developed has three actors: Student, Teacher and Administrator. Below is the Use Case Diagram for the system.

Figure 4: 3.7.3.0 Use Case Diagram

3.7.0 Class Diagram

Class diagrams are the main building block of any object-oriented solution. It shows the classes in a system, attributes, and operations of each class and the relationship between each class.

In most modeling tools, a class has three parts. Name at the top, attributes in the middle and operations or methods at the bottom. In a large system with many related classes, classes are grouped together to create class diagrams. Different relationships between classes are shown by different types of arrows. The classes used in the study include: Adm in, teacher, department, Class, student, marks and

subject. Below is an image

of a class diagram for the system.

Figure 5: 3.7.3.1 Class Diagram

3.7.4 Physical Database Design

Below are the Twelve (12) database tables that were designed and used for the system.

Table 4: 3.7.4.0 Name: tbladmin

Attribute	Data type	Constraint
ID	int	Primary key(A.I)
AdminName	varchar	
UserName	varchar	
MobileNumber	bigint	
Email	varchar	
Password	varchar	
AdminRegdate	timestamp	

The table above shows which type of the information is captured on for adm in user and this include ID. Admin Name, User Name, Mobile Number, Email, Password and Admin Registration date.

Table 5: 3.7.4.1 Name: student _table

Attribute	1):11:1 IN pc	(oils! rain'
Id	int	Primary key(A.1)
Unique_id	int	
Student name	varchar	
Picture	varchar	
date_of birth	varchar	
date_first_	varchar	
guardian_name	varchar	
guardian_number	varchar	
exam number	varchar	
student_grade	varchar	
student_class	varchar	
student sex	varchar	
student_age	int	
student address	varchar	
Subjects	varchar	

The Table above shows the details of the student which includes Id, unique id, student name, student picture, date of birth, date of first entry into any school, guardian name, guardian contact number, student, exam number, student grade, student class, student sex, student age, student address and subjects.

Table 6: 3.7.4.2 Name: thlteacher

Attributes	Data type	Constraints
ID	int	Primary key
Unique_id	int	
Name	varchar	
Picture	varchar	
Email	varchar	
MobileNumber	varchar	
TSNumber	varchar	
EmployeeNumber	varchar	
Sex	varchar	
NRCNumber	varchar	
Qualification	varchar	
Address	varchar	
Department	varchar	
FirstAppointmentDate	varchar	
RegDate	timestamp	

The table above shows the details of the teacher and how they are captured in the data base.

Table 7: 3.7.4.3 Name: l bldpartmentl

Attributes	Data type	Constraint
ID	int	Primary key(A.I)
Department	varchar	
CreationDate	timestamp	

The table above shows the details of the department and how they are captured in the data base. They include department name and the date the department was created.

Table S: 3.7.4.4 Name: table marks

Attribute	Data type	Constraint
Id	int	Primary key(A.I)
unique_id	int	
student_name	varchar	
exam_number	varchar	
Term	varchar	
Subject	varchar	
week5	varchar	
Week I 0	varchar	
endOfTerm	varchar	

The table above shows the details about student marks.

Table 9: 3.7,4.5 Name: student users

Attribute	Data type	Constraint
Id	ail	Primary key(A.I)
unique_id	int	
Surname	varchar	
Firstname	varchar	
Username	varchar	
Grade_class	varchar	
Password	varchar	

The table provided contains details required for a student to sign up and create an account. These details typically include:

1. Surname: The student's last name or family name.
2. First Name: The student's first name or given name.
3. Username: A unique username or identifier that the student will use to log in to their account.
4. Class: The class or grade to which the student belongs, often used for educational and organizational purposes.
5. Password: A secure and confidential password chosen by the student to protect their account.

These details are essential for creating a user account and ensuring secure access to a system or platform. Students provide this information during the registration process to set up their account for various online services or applications.

Table 10: 3.7.4.6 Name: teneher_users

Attribute	Data type	Constraint
Id	Int	Primary kcy(A.I)
unique id	Int	
Surname	varchar	
Firstname	varchar	
Email	varchar	
Username	varchar	
Password	varchar	

The table provided contains details required for a teacher to sign up and create an account. These details typically include:

Surname: The teacher's last name or family name.

First Name: The teacher's first name or given name.

Email Address: The teacher's email address, which is often used for communication and account verification.

Username: A unique username or identifier that the teacher will use to log in to their account.

Password: A secure and confidential password chosen by the teacher to protect their account.

These details are essential for creating a user account and ensuring secure access to a system or platform. Teachers provide this information during the registration process to set up their account for various online services or applications.

Table 11: 3.7.4.7 Name: class table

Attributes	Data type	Constraint
Id	Int	Primary key(A.I)
Unique_id	Int	
grade	varchar	
class	varchar	
CreationDate	timestamp	

The table above shows the details about class and how they are captured in the data base. They include grade. Class and the date the class was created.

Table 12: 3.7.4.N Name: student Ides

,thrilinte Id	Data type	Constraint
	int	Primary key(A I)
unique_i(I	int	
Sender name	varchar	
Student number	varchar	
name	varchar	
size	int	
downloads	int	
Uploadeddate	varchar	

The table above shows the details about files (documents) that a student receives from the school administration.

Table 13: 3.7.4.9 Name: files

Attribute	Data type	Constraint
Id	int	Primary key(A.1)
random id	int	
unique_id	varchar	
name	varchar	
size	int	
downloads	int	

The table above shows the details about personal files for a teacher those are uploaded and downloaded.

Table 14: 3.7.4.10 Name: shared tiles

Attribute	Data type	Constraint
Id	int	Primary key(A.I)
unique_id	int	
Sender name	varchar	
Receiver id	varchar	
Name	varchar	
Size	int	
downloads	int	
Uploaded date	varchar	

The table above shows the details about files shared among teachers and admin.

Table 15: 3.7.4.11 Name: AdminReceived info

Attribute	Data type	Constraint
Id	int	Primary key(A.1)
unique_id	int	
Sender name	varchar	
description	varchar	
Admin contact	varchar	
Name	varchar	
Size	int	
downloads	int	
Date_uploaded	varchar	
comment		

The table above shows the details about files (documents) that are received by the school administration from teachers and students.

Chapter 4: Findings (Data Presentation, Analysis, & Discussions)

4.0 Introduction

This chapter delves into the data presentation, analysis, and discussions of the study's findings. The analysis is conducted in the context of the reviewed literature and specific research objectives.

4.1 Data Presentation

The research was conducted across six schools, with Mushona Primary School serving as the central focus of the study. Data collection was executed through the distribution of questionnaires and interviews.

The targeted study population consisted of 40 individuals, including 6 administrators, 10 teachers, 14 students, 5 parents, and 5 non-students. All questionnaires distributed to the respondents were returned, resulting in a 100% attrition rate.

Among the target population, 34 individuals were in favor of the proposed system, 4 were against it, and 2 were undecided. The findings indicated that 85% of respondents within these schools expressed support for the proposed system, 10% were opposed to it, and 5% remained undecided.

4.1 Data analysis

The data was analyzed using the pie chart as shown below

Figure 6: Data Analysis: Response rate

YESNO

UNDECIDED

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS 4,0 Conclusion

Conclusions

Based on the findings and in alignment with the research objectives, it can be concluded that the Online School Record Management System will effectively achieve its primary objectives of improving the storage of information concerning teachers and students. This system offers a paperless record-keeping and viewing process and allows access to information at any time, provided there is an internet service.

The system streamlines operations by reducing the manpower required in waiting and reception departments. Data retrieval times are notably reduced compared to the previously used manual system. Additionally, the system automates the management of historical records, requiring less manpower for this task.

The implementation of this system will enhance accuracy in various aspects of record management. Data validation and verification procedures significantly minimize human errors. As data is validated upon entry, the occurrence of human errors is greatly reduced.

5.1 Recommendations

The recommendations stemming from the Online School Record Management System for further development and implementation are as follows:

- Schools should consider adopting an online school record management system to address challenges such as information loss, cost reduction, data duplication, and efficient information retrieval.
- As the system is implemented and adopted in schools, it is advisable to involve stakeholders such as parents as active users, allowing them to access information or records concerning their children.
- Recognizing that School Record Management is a multifaceted domain, students and individuals interested in expanding this system should be encouraged to explore other aspects of School Record Management, including store records, financial records, guidance and counseling records, and more.

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APPENDICES

Questionnaire

We are students from Zambia ICT College. We are currently undertaking a research project that will lead to an award in bachelor's degree of ICT with Education. Any help rendered to us will be greatly used and highly utilized.

Table 16: Research Questionnaire

S/N	Question	Answers
1	Name	
2	Job title	
3	Phone number (optional)	
4	How do you keep records for students and Teachers currently? (Tick one)	☐ Manual ☐ Computerized
5	How does it work?	
6	How is the student' personal data captured?	
7	How is the information stored after it is captured?	
8	How the records are identified and retrieved.	
9	What challenges do you face when collecting and retrieving data from the current system of the students	
10	What are the general limitations of the current paper based system?	
11	Do you think the Online School Records Management System will improve the effectiveness of managing the records?	
12	What are the recommendations of Online School Record Management System for capturing, storing and retrieving of the Results	

Thanks a lot for your cooperation.